

PSYCHOLOGICAL CHARACTERISTICS OF TWINS AND THEIR DIFFERENTIAL DIFFERENTIATION

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Annotation: *In this article, the unique distinguishing features of twins and the scientific theoretical basis of the twin method are mentioned.*

Key words: *personality, psychological characteristics, twins, psychology of twins, monozygote, dizygote, social environment, psychological development.*

Аннотация: *В данной статье упоминаются уникальные отличительные черты близнецов и научно-теоретическая основа близнецового метода.*

Ключевые слова: *личность, психологические особенности, близнецы, психология близнецов, монозигота, дизигота, социальная среда, психологическое развитие.*

Relevance of the topic.

Several studies have been conducted on them to study the psychology of twins. On the basis of these studies, scientists used a lot of scientific work, studying the Twins, having separated the twins from each other by means of several methods. When studied using the method of twins, the genetic aspects of the environment in their development were taken into account. The result showed that the properties in the pigs are similar to each other than genetically removed. As an example, they separated one of the Twins for a year to adapt them to another environment. They have been observed by researchers for over a year. During this time, coincidences encountered in the life of one occurred even in the second.

The fact is that if we study the individual psychological characteristics of the Twins, in addition to the differentiation between them, there are problems of comparison, depending on whether they are same-sex or different-sex. At the same time, in the conditions of Uzbekistan, we are attracted by the fact that little attention is paid to this issue. What we focus on while studying the problem.

First: the link of the indicators of the development of twins with mintalethite. That is, in the characteristics of each age of the Twins lies the question of socialization, which is visible to the eye.

Secondly: the similarity in the psychology of the Twins or the recognition of the dependent side in such a way as to relate to the characteristics of the character, to which they are formed in the cell.

That is, it is distinguished by the fact that this issue, as a level of relevance, is poorly addressed.

The fact that the Twins in the community work together as a co-operative many achievements cannot be called is not so. They rely on one another in their activities, and one overshadows the other. Psychologists first of all take into account the conditions of adaptation in the environment, as they study the individual characteristics of the individual. In the following years, studies in psychological laboratories have shown a wide effective way of diagnosing the divergence characteristics of the vertebral vertebrae from each other. Within the methodologies commonly used in the research, Langityud's methodology focuses on the study of the Twins. The purpose of this methodology is to obtain higher nerve activity and other properties of temperament of the curiosity of the feeling of similarity in the Twins the differentiation in them. French psychologists on this methodology P.Zazes and Sh.Blyulers also learned.

Brother Oka E.Dey and Devis conducted an exhibition on 80 pairs of twins from the age of 2 to the age of 5 with the aim of studying the Twins. The E.Dey believes that in comparison with other children who have reached this age, the size of the Twins will be smaller. The E.Davis insists that the jusses will be among his peers when the Twins reach the age of five or six. Psychologist R. According to the interpretation of zazzo, the development of dizygotic twins in relation to monozygotic twins accelerates the adaptability to the social environment. In comparison with other twins, the girl twins, developed in two eggs, become more agile. Most of the time in the present day the Twins are engaged in various activities that are in harmony with their interests and needs. Such cases are observed in the male twins. Because they strive to become independent from their youth.¹

The comparison of one-egg and two-egg twins is important for the field of psychology, since by comparing one-egg twins, the answer to psychological questions cannot be obtained. Scientists believe that from the first days of their lives one-ovary and two-ovary twins grow up under the same conditions, for example, that the same signs that are in monozygotic twins do not even exist in

¹ Morozova T Features of work with children-twins National education 2009 No. 1-with 269 -271

dizygote. Previously it was written that these are simply factors related to the breed. But as already mentioned above, Monozygotes and dizygotes are the same the environment does not grow to the conditions. Adults encourage monozygotes to behave more evenly than dizygotes.

Developed from two eggs, twins can be of different sexes, and they simply become similar to each other in style, which is no different from Akka sisters.

At the last time, in genetic studies, a method is used, which consists in comparing the similarity of Monozygotic and dizygotic twins living in at a certain time interval in pairs. After growing up, the Twins get married and go to different climates. Their relationship remains episodic. If the similarity of the twins who lived in for a long time did not differ from the similarity of the twins who lived together, it can be concluded that external conditions do not affect their similarity. If during the time when the twins lived in a single isolated state, the similarity of some psychological characteristics is lost, then it can be said that the conditions of the affect the characteristics under study. In the method of fully separated twins, it is also possible to determine to what extent the postulate in the Equality point in of Monozygotic and dizygotic twins is observed. If the monozygotic twins who live in differ from each other according to some psychological characteristic, then the dizygotic twins who live in do not differ from the dizygotic twins who live together according to their differences in pairs. And this is due to the fact that the comparative conditions of Monozygotic and dizygotic twins are not correctly established, and the data on the heredity of the characteristic studied from classical studies of twins indicate that this characteristic has increased fertility.

The method of the families of monozygotic twins, or the method of monozygotic hemispheres, is an expression from the comparison of children in the family who are one of the father or mother monozygotic twins. These children have a specific genetic status: Emma or uncle can be viewed from a genetic point of view as the father or mother herself. They are not brothers or sisters, without being siblings, because they have one genetically different parent, so Ham calls them half-siblings. This method manifests itself in a mixture of the method of twins and families. In this is studied by family members of a pair of large twins. According to the genetic constitutions of the children of the monozygotic twins, the subspecies is the same as the children of one person from different marriages. With this method, it is possible to determine the effect of motherhood by studying the monozygotic male and female pairs of twins and their offspring. Through this method, as well as for the extensive study of the hereditary causes of a number of diseases in which one of the pigs with Monozygotic does not get sick while the

other does not. For example, it turned out that the disease with schizophrenia can be encountered in one or two of the Twins in their relatives, despite the fact that they are suffering from this disease. The main task of this method is to determine the effect of motherhood. With this term, not only through the transmission of genes, but also psychological, postnatal factors (the identity of the child with the mother is characteristic of their interaction), biological and cases of maternal stomach (the case of the mother's organism in the period, the cytoplasmic degeneration) are characterized by a strong influence on the phenotype of the descendants of the. The maternal effect is manifested by a greater similarity in psychological qualities in children who have a monozygotic mother than in children who have a monozygotic father. The main interest is the occurrence of the effect of cytoplasmic it is possible to determine only in this way (in the psychological signs of a person).² The fact is that in the genes included in the nucleus of chromosome cells, some structures that carry hereditary information are in the cytoplasm cell outside the nucleus (these two types of heredity are called "core", "chromosomal" and "cytoplasmic"). The volume of cytoplasm in the female egg cell can not be compared with its volume in the sperm: according to some data, in the egg cell it is about a thousand times more than sperm consisting of nuclei and layers. Therefore, all the cytoplasmic structures that pass on to the next generation pass through the mother - this is the genetic motherhood effect. According to the effect of motherhood, this experimental model allows the phenomenon of balky to forestall the expected choice of a couple. In the last case, if their mother is monozygotic son children will be more like each other if their father is monozygotic, they will be less similar. We can observe the opposite of this circumstance in the girl-boy semi-sibling.

Twins are usually introverted, which can not be communicated, especially if they are monozygotic. They observed that they are less likely to marry than single children if the Twins are dizygotic the first-born child is orientated to an adult, becomes a leader and takes all responsibility. The second in this shell itself will be soft, carefree and cheerful. In one egg-cell twins, however, usually the leader is not manifested. Such twins establish weak relationships with their parents by establishing mutually independent relationships, they are very angry with each other, which gives birth to the of separating them in school. Twins always want to have the same thing so that they do not prevail over one-over the other.

² Malykh S. B., Egorova M. S., Meshkova T. A. Psychogenetics. T 1: Textbook for universities. – SPb.: Peter, 2008. - 142-bet.

Due to their unusual attitude to the twins, they grow up in a peculiar atmosphere from early childhood. Most of the surrounding people perceive the pair of twins as an integral, which cannot be distinguished from each other, and do not pay attention to the differences in children they call them by their last name or by one name. As indicated in some sources, the appeal of parents in the family environment would be similar in comparison with dizygotic twins in monozygotic twins.

Although there is not enough scientific data on the psychology of twins in our country, however, from Uzbek scientists Gaziev, N.Majidov carried out scientific research and contributed to the development of psychology with a number of monographs, manuals and scientific articles. On the development of the psychology of Gemini in the former Soviet psychology (Z.M Zirina, S.D. P'yankov, E.A Sergienko, E.A Ryazanova, G.A Vilenskaya, G.K Ushakova, V.C Mukhina), psychogenetic aspects of the difference of the Twins from one another are differentiated from other psychologists (, Kanaev II, Elizabeth M. Bryan, Patricia Malmstrom, Klein M.D), comparison according to different gender (R.Zazza, F.Galton. The A.Fershuer), the influence of social factors (Luriya, Gezell a, Bomsma D,), such scientists have studied.

For example, in 1975 year Australia and B. In British schools, surveys were conducted on the level of assimilation of pigs. According to the result of the conducted surveys, 10-year-old boy twins were born alone, while the girl was 14 years old, the boy observed in the twins while the reading and writing of the twins were seriously lagging behind, and less lagging behind, while the girl children (except for the boy children) were getting their peers to be born alone. While more than 70% of girls at the same age have enough reading and writing skills to live in the Society of Eurasia. For example, they read and understand the journal. And in the boy children this indicator was 40%. It turns out that the mental potential of girls showed a patent above the mental potential of boys. In most children, the ability to understand and mastering the information that he / she has read constitutes an average level. More than half of the Twins are left behind in reading, and they can be called that. For example, he came to the conclusion that he "does not know how to read". In England, a methodology has been developed that helps to determine the initial level of children. This is mainly due to the fact that he began to study, and the subsequent period is aimed at studying the changes in his studies. Here, not only will the final results be taken into account, but also check what changes the child will experience from growth at the initial level. If the child falls back from his peers at the beginning, then at the middle stage it will develop again.

In 2000, 2,6% of the children admitted to school were twins. In the same year, when conducting a survey among children, the difference in the incidence of children born with twins and alone was low. Gemini is less lagging behind in reading and accounting. Experiments in the UK have attracted more children to themselves than tests conducted in Australia because in the majority of the research conducted, the psychologist has been able to deal with the twins alone. In such a process, the difference between children born alone and twins is almost invisible. In the Australian experiment, it shows that the main problem of the son child twins is neglect and laziness. For example: the 14-year-old twin boy said the clock was more wrong depending on the clock and made a mistake in multiplying the numbers. This does not mean that he has bad abilities, that he does not try to find the right answer because he cannot concentrate his attention, which will certainly affect the reading.³ When a child reads the word "mail" as "barrel", this is due to his correct reading, and the content of it is considered secondary. Three such problems are more common in the pigs. For example: when a child sees a word, he thinks that it is a word that begins with another letter of the same length. Of course, this is also the case with children born alone but they say that more often meet in the Twins teacher and mother. Some children, let it be twins, let it be children born alone they study well. Reading to other children is with great difficulty, because they will master the remaining school subjects even worse. Such children cannot be called by the term cannot read well. They have mastered all the sciences more or less reading will suffer such a loss. To determine if a child cannot read Well, it is necessary to first determine whether the child can read or not. Such diagnostics can be conducted by a teacher and a psychologist or other specialist. If the child has attention disorders, it is more difficult to determine his or her abilities, since it should be taken into account that in solving any arithmetic example, mental activity is necessary.

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